

EFFECT OF JUTE ON THE HYDROLYTIC DEGRADATION OF POLY(LACTIC ACID)

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the effect of jute fibre on the hydrolysis of poly(lactic acid)(PLA) in deionized water under 60 °C. Water absorption, mechanical properties, glass transition temperature (T_g) and crystallinity degree ($\chi\%$) were characterized. It was found that jute fibre could increase the water absorption of jute/PLA composites compared to neat PLA for its large number of hydrophilic vessels and sieve tube, but it did not cause a decrease in mechanical properties of composites. On the contrary, the mechanical properties of jute/PLA composites were higher than that of PLA at the same aging time for the hindrance of jute fibre to the vibration and mobility of PLA molecular chain resulting slower hydrolysis of jute/PLA composites compared with neat PLA.

1 INTRODUCTION

Green renewable materials have received more attentions for their completely biodegradation, which are an effective way to solve the problems of depletion of oil resources and environmental pollution by partly alternate commercial oil-derived polymers such as polypropylene, polyethylene and polystyrene. Among all commercial biopolymers, nature fibre reinforced PLA composites are one of the most attractive material for their good biodegradation and high-modulus [1, 2, 3]. Now nature fibre/PLA composites are widely applied in the field aerospace and automotive, e.g. Toray have already started application of kenaf/PLA composite materials in automobile trunk lid [4]. But the environment changing can take place during the use of those products, which can cause the aging of composites. So it is very meaningful to research on their aging behavior and control the using life.

As a linear aliphatic thermoplastic polyester produced from renewable resources, PLA can be decomposed into H₂O and CO₂ at the end [5, 6, 7]. Hydrolysis is one of the main characteristics of PLA. It can affect the mechanical property, which determines the service life of PLA. There were many work have been done to study the hydrolysis of PLA [8-15]. Both chain end scission and random chain cleavage for PLA hydrolysis have been reported in previous work. Hydrolytic degradation behavior and mechanism depend on chemical structure, morphology, hydrolysis conditions. Nature fibres were widely used to reinforce polymer matrix due to their advantages such as low cost, low weight and biodegradability. But the nature fibre, because of it contains many hydroxyl groups, which is suited to absorb water, can greatly affect hygroscopicity of composites. There are also many other influences in the hydrolysis of PLA, like the crystallinity and thermal property. Although natural fibre was used to make composites with PLA, no exactly conclusion has been made regarding on the effect of natural fibre on the hydrolysis of PLA, which should be solved in the development of natural fibre reinforced PLA composites.

Bodros et al. [15] found an improvement of strength of PLA composites with increasing flax fiber content up to the level where fiber agglomeration take place. Ndazi et al. [14] studied the hydrolytic degradations of poly(lactic acid)/rice hulls(PLA/RH) composites with various rice hulls contents due to water absorption at different temperature. The results attested that the stability of PLA/RH composites in water depended slightly on rice hulls but it was significantly influenced by water temperature. Oever et al. [11] stated that melt flow index analysis and intrinsic viscosity indicated that the effect of the different levels of moisture in the fibre had a similar and small effect on PLA

degradation during processing, PLA hydrolysis appeared rather affected by fibre diameter. Morphology, flexural strength and stiffness and impact of the composites were not significantly affected by the water present in the undried fibre.

The aim of this study was to investigate on the hydrolysis affection of PLA with addition of jute fibre under hydrothermal environment. The aging mechanism was analysed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA)($M_w=150,000$) was obtained from Shuzhou Jiwang Environmentally Friendly Material Co. Ltd., China. Jute fibre (JF) was supplied by Shanghai Qiancong Jute Fibre Co. Ltd., China.

2.2 Specimen preparation

First jute fibres and PLA were dried under vacuum at 80 °C for 4h. Then the dried jute fibres and PLA granules were melted in a twin-screw extruder at the same time. The temperature at the feed section of twin-screw extruder was 175 °C decreasing to 155 °C at the outlet. In order to set jute fibres at 10%wt, the feed section of twin-screw extruder was set at 25Hz and screw rotation speed was fixed at 20Hz. The jute/PLA composites were granulated and dried under vacuum at 80 °C for 4h. Then the pure PLA and composites were injection molded into mechanical test specimens respectively by using a WHY-W (Dahua, China) injection-moulding machine with a barrel temperature of 175 °C.

2.3 Water absorption

The water absorption test sample ($30 \times 20 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$) were pre-dried in a vacuum oven at 40 °C for 4h. Quintuplicate specimens of each sample were weighed as initial mass (M_0) and then set in the deionized water baths under 60 °C. At a predetermined time, each specimen was picked out, wiped out the water on the surface and recorded the weight gain (M_t). The water absorption was calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Water absorption (\%)} = \frac{M_t - M_0}{M_0} \times 100$$

All the values presented were averaged from five specimens.

2.4 Mechanical properties measurement

The tensile and flexural properties were measured on a WHY-W machine (Chengde instruments Ltd., China). The tensile testing according to GB/T 1447-2005 and crosshead speed was 2mm/min. The flexural testing according to GB/T 1449-2005 at a support length of 64 mm and a crosshead speed of 2mm/min, the size of flexural testing samples was $80 \times 10 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$.

2.5 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurement was carried out by a Q20 thermal analysis system (TA, USA). The samples (4-5 mg) were heated from 20 °C to 200 °C at 10 °C/min. Glass transition temperature (T_g) and cold crystallization temperature (T_c) was estimated based on the first scan. Melting temperature (T_m) refers to the highest-temperature peak of the melting endotherm during 1st heating ramp. Crystallinity degree ($\chi(\%)$) was calculated by the following formula:

$$\chi(\%) = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_m^0 \cdot (1 - \Phi_{JF})} \times 100\%$$

where ΔH_c , ΔH_m and ΔH_m^0 are the enthalpies of cold crystallization, melting and melting of fully crystalline PLA, which can be found in the literature to be 91.3 J/g[16]. Φ_{JF} is the content of jute fibre

in jute/PLA composites.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Water absorption

Figure 1 shows the results of the % weight gain (M_t) as function of $t^{1/2}$ by PLA and jute/PLA composites at 60 °C, respectively. There were three regimes on moisture absorption: (1) a quickly water absorption, (2) the % weight gain maintained balance in a short time then increased to saturation, (3) the % weight gain began to decline.

Figure 1: Weigh gain (%) changes of PLA and jute/PLA composites with $t^{1/2}$

In the first stage of the two curves, a linear relationship between M_t and $t^{1/2}$ was observed. This indicated that the water absorption of PLA and jute/PLA composites followed the Fickian law of diffusion [17], which was a simple water in-diffusion. The absorption of jute/PLA composites increased faster than PLA. It was because jute fiber contains large number of vessels and sieve tube, which promoted the transport of water. In the second stage, the two curves diverted from the Fickian law. It was thought that the water molecules diffuse into composites then irreversible physical and chemical reaction happened. It was shown that jute/PLA composites reveal saturation with the M_t of 4.48% after about 28 days, which was much higher than the saturation value of PLA (1.01%) after 7 days. This was due to the existence of hydrophilic hydroxyl groups of jute fiber in composites, which promoted the water absorption of composites. The emergence of crack in PLA matrix with time increase caused the second water absorption. Due to the degradation of PLA and composites, lot of lactic acid molecules diffused into deionized water, the M_t began to decline after saturation.

Figure 2: Effect of hydrolysis time on tensile properties of PLA and composites under 60 °C, (a) tensile strength, (b) tensile modulus

Figure 3: Effect of hydrolysis time on flexural properties of PLA and composites under 60 °C, (c) flexural strength, (d) flexural modulus

3.2 Mechanical properties

Figure 2 and Figure 3 showed the effect of hydrolysis time on tensile and flexural properties of PLA and composites immersed in deionized water under 60 °C. The tensile strength of pure PLA was 64.6MPa decreased to 58.1MPa after added jute fiber. There was the same trend of flexural strength. This was because the jute fiber as short fiber, whose ratio of length to diameter not reach the critical value, only serves as a filler. The tensile strength and flexural strength of PLA and composites was reduced with time increasing, respectively. However, the mechanical strength of jute/PLA composites decreased slower than that of pure PLA. After one week aging, the tensile strength of PLA decreased to 19.9MPa, which was closed to the tensile strength of jute/PLA composites (16.1MPa) after aging two weeks. The tensile strength of PLA at 60 °C was difficult to measure by using a WHY-W machine at hydrolysis time of two weeks. The rapid decline was caused by the drastic degradations. There were similar changes to flexural strength. Therefore, it can be see that adding of jute fiber made the

composites degradation delayed a week compared to pure PLA. This was because the degradation rate of jute fiber was smaller than that of pure PLA. The jute fiber in composites can inhibit vibration and mobility of PLA molecular chain resulting slower hydrolysis of jute/PLA composites compared with pure PLA.

The tensile modulus of jute/PLA composites samples, before aging, was higher than PLA because the jute fiber have high tensile modulus. Tensile modulus of pure PLA marginally decreased after one week hydrothermal ageing for a large number of cracks caused by degradations. However, there was an increase in tensile modulus of jute/PLA after aging one week then it had a decrease as time went on. This may be due to the degradation, lots of lactic acid molecules emerged, which made jute/PLA composites brittle. With time goes on, appearance of numbers of voids and cracking lead a subsequently decrease of tensile modulus of jute/PLA composites. The flexural modulus of PLA had a decline after two week aging similar to the tensile modulus change. The flexural modulus and tensile modulus of jute/PLA composites were consistent in trend before two weeks aging. While, the flexural modulus has a continuous improvement at the third week, which was different from the tensile modulus for existence of lots of water.

3.3 Calorimetric analysis

By differential scanning calorimetry, the thermal property has been investigated to further study the effect of jute fibre on the hydrolysis of PLA. Fig. 4 shows the heating DSC curves of each sample. A summary of DSC results is reported in Table 1. Glass transition temperature (T_g) of PLA was lower than that of jute/PLA at same hydrolysis time. This was because jute fibre in PLA inhibited vibration and mobility of PLA molecular chain declined the T_g of jute/PLA composites. T_g of PLA decreased after hydrolysis, which may be contributed by the reduction of molecular weight (M_n). After 14 days

Figure 4: DSC of a) PLA and b) jute/PLA composites at different hydrolysis time in deionized water.

aging, it disappeared due to the increase of crystallinity. There was not too much change of T_g of jute/PLA composites before aging 28 days for the adding of jute fibre.

For the not hydrolysed jute/PLA, the cold crystalline was very obvious. With the increase of aging time, the cold crystalline disappeared while a strong peak of melting endotherm emerged in the curves. This means that the composites have perfect crystalline and high crystallinity. The pure PLA specimens have the same tendency. The crystallinity of PLA showed an evident increase from 37.05% to 76.79% after 28 days immersion in water, which bring about surface whitening and loss of transparency. On one hand, the high temperature and plasticizing effect of water promoted recrystallization of amorphous, which can increase crystallinity degree. On the other hand, this may be related to the erosion of the amorphous parts lead to the increase of crystallinity degree because the

hydrolysis is easier occurred in amorphous [18]. It can be seen from Table 1, the crystalline degree of jute/PLA composites was higher than neat PLA at the same aging time. This may be related to the hindrance of jute fibre to the motion of PLA segments. The melting peak temperature measured during the first heating scan decreases with time, revealing that the crystalline regions were also affected by the hydrolysis process.

Sample		Days of hydrolysis				
		0	7	14	21	28
PLA	T _g [°C]	60.85	57.76	-	-	-
	T _m [°C]	168.75	167.33	155.66	155.75	135.73
	χ[%]	37.05	41.04	55.91	57.27	76.79
Jute/PLA	T _g [°C]	61.17	61.82	61.99	61.56	60.53
	T _m [°C]	164.06	163.66	166.23	162.93	148.66
	χ[%]	15.47	37.88	35.17	36.77	41.33

Table 1: Summary of DSC results: T_g, T_m and crystallinity degree (χ[%]) was Measured during 1st heating ramp (at 10 °C/min).

4 CONCLUSIONS

By study the hydrolytic degradation of PLA and jute/PLA composites in deionized water at 60 °C, water absorption, mechanical properties and thermal analysis has been studied to reveal the effect of jute fibre on the hydrolysis of PLA. Though jute fibre could increase the water absorption of composites compared to neat PLA for its large number of hydrophilic vessels and sieve tube, it did not cause a decrease in mechanical properties of composites. On the contrary, the mechanical properties of jute/PLA composites was higher than that of PLA at the same aging time. This was because the adding of jute fiber delayed the hydrolysis of PLA for hindering the action of PLA segment. Which was also confirmed by the thermal analysis. The results will be benefit for improving the thermostability of PLA to push the applying of jute/PLA materials in practical fields.

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